

DIRECT MEASUREMENT OF OUT-OF-PLANE AND IN-PLANE CURE SHRINKAGE STRAIN IN COMPOSITES BY EMBEDDED FIBER-OPTIC SENSORS

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1 Introduction

Within thermoset fiber-reinforced composites under cure, the matrix resin undergoes cross-linking reactions accompanied by chemically-induced volumetric shrinkage. The resin changes its physical state from a liquid to a rubbery-like material (i.e., gelation), finally reaching a glassy solid (i.e., vitrification). When the resin is in the liquid state, the chemical cure shrinkage is accommodated by the resin flow and will not induce stress in the composite. After gelation, however, the resin stiffness increases and effective mechanical interaction between the resin and the reinforcing fibers is established, leading to stress development in curing composite. Since cure-driven composite shrinkage after gelation, especially in the resin-dominated transverse direction, significantly affects shape distortion and damage initiation of composite products through residual stress/strain development [1-3], several dilatometric techniques (e.g., capillary-type dilatometer, gravimetric method, rheometer, and thermo-mechanical analyzer (TMA)) have been proposed and utilized to characterize and model cure shrinkage of thermoset resins and their composites, as recently reviewed in Ref. [4]. However, most of the instruments work under conditions that do not match industrial processes as in an autoclave. Also these techniques are not applicable to in-situ characterization of practical composite parts with complex shape (e.g., L-shaped corner part), where significant shape distortion arises. Recently, embedded fiber-optic sensors are attracting considerable attention as a sensing device for structural health monitoring (SHM) and also as a tool for in-situ process characterization of complex-shaped composite parts cured in industrial conditions [4-6]. Optical fiber sensors are highly

sensitive, small with diameter less than 150 μ m, and can be embedded in composite materials with minimal invasive manner and without significant effects on the global mechanical behavior of the host material. Several studies utilized fiber-optic sensors for in-situ process monitoring of thermosetting composite [7-18]. Some of them could capture chemical cure shrinkage strain in composite laminates after the onset of gelation (i.e., after the effective interface bonding is established between the resin, the reinforcing fibers, and the sensors). However, optical fiber sensors were always embedded in composite in-plane directions even though through-thickness cure shrinkage is the key deformation [1-3], and the measured strain values were only less than 100 μ ϵ in general. Furthermore, the physical meaning of the measured strain has not been sufficiently discussed.

This study advances the fiber-optic-based technique for in-situ characterization of direction-dependent cure shrinkage. A new technique to embed a fiber Bragg grating (FBG) sensor in composite out-of-plane directions is established (Fig. 1), directly

Fig. 1 Embedding FBG sensor in out-of-plane direction in addition to conventional in-plane sensor.

measuring the key through-thickness cure shrinkage under an industrial condition. In combination with “double-sided vacuum bagging” (i.e., no-mold cure) and “demolding during curing” techniques, sensors embedded in through-thickness and in-plane directions clarify direction-dependent cure shrinkage in autoclaved unidirectional carbon/epoxy, demonstrating the flexibility and potential of the developed technique.

2 Establishing Through-Thickness Sensor Technique

2.1 FBG Sensor

An FBG is a part of a single-mode silica optical fiber having periodic variation in the core refractive index [19] (Fig. 2). When broadband light is launched into the FBG sensor, a narrow spectral component is reflected back. The center wavelength of the reflected light, λ_B , is given by

$$\lambda_B = 2n\Lambda, \quad (1)$$

where n and Λ are the effective refractive index and the grating period. When strain ε in the sensor axial direction and temperature change ΔT are applied to the FBG, the spectrum center wavelength λ_B shifts by

$$\Delta\lambda_B = C_S\varepsilon + \Delta\lambda_{BT}(\Delta T), \quad (2)$$

where C_S is the wavelength-strain sensitivity and $\Delta\lambda_{BT}(\Delta T)$ is the thermally-induced shift function, both of which can be determined in preliminary

Fig. 2 FBG sensor.

calibration tests. In order to obtain the FBG axial strain ε from the measured wavelength shift $\Delta\lambda_B$, it is necessary to decouple the strain and temperature contributions to the wavelength shift (Eq. (2)). Even though several fiber-optic-based temperature compensation techniques have been proposed, this study simply utilizes thermo-couples embedded near FBG sensors to measure the temperature change ΔT , and then calculates the strain ε from the equation,

$$\varepsilon = \frac{\Delta\lambda_B - \Delta\lambda_{BT}(\Delta T)}{C_S}. \quad (3)$$

2.2 Embedding Optical Fiber Sensor in Through-Thickness Direction

Figure 3 depicts a schematic of the embedding/bagging procedure established. It is important to note that this study utilized a prepreg-based process. However, the technique is applicable, without difficulty, to other types of manufacturing process with single-sided molds (e.g., vacuum assisted resin transfer molding (VaRTM)). And even in double-sided mold processes like RTM, slight modification of the mold may allow its application. First, prepregs were stacked while inserting a thin needle with diameter less than 1 mm, making a small through-thickness hole without damaging the reinforcing fibers. After lay-up, the needle was removed and the FBG sensor was then inserted into the hole. The position of the FBG sensor is controllable by changing the thickness of the base laminate without a hole and the “tail length” of the FBG sensor (Fig. 3). Finally, a release film, a breather fabric, and a vacuum bag film covered the laminate, as in a conventional bagging process, and a hole made on the bagging film to extract the FBG sensor was sealed. Figure 4 shows the surface of an autoclave-cured carbon/epoxy specimen after demolding. An optical fiber sensor is perpendicularly coming out from the surface. Even though the surface was rough due to the print of the breather fabric, the sensor-extracting area was flat and no surface bump was seen, confirming the minimal disturbance in the composite by embedding the sensor in the through-thickness direction.

Fig. 3 Schematic of sensor embedding procedure.

Fig. 4 Optical fiber perpendicularly coming out from surface.

Fig. 5 Stress transfer from curing composite to optical fiber, and consequent deformation. It is assumed that composite behaves elastically.

2.3 Evaluating Sensitivity of Short-Tailed FBG Sensor By Considering Shear-Lag Effect

Since FBG sensors are embedded in the through-thickness direction of relatively thin composite laminates, one cannot use long-tailed FBG sensors. For example, when we embed an FBG sensor at the through-thickness center, the tail of the FBG sensor should be less than half the laminate thickness. Hence, this section evaluates sensitivity of short-tailed FBG sensors by considering shear-lag effect at the sensor tail [20]. Figure 5 depicts a schematic of stress transfer from a curing composite to an optical fiber, and their consequent deformation. The optical fiber is embedded in the composite transverse direction, and it is assumed that the curing composite behaves elastically. As described above, after gelation, effective interfacial bond develops between the curing composite and the optical fiber, and cure shrinkage strain of the composite begins to be transferred to the optical fiber mainly through interfacial shear stress arising at the edge of the optical fiber. At the beginning, since the curing resin and thus the composite is soft, the interfacial shear stress is low, and the stress transfer length d , over which the strain in the optical fiber reaches the far-field strain in the composite, is long [20]. As the cure reaction proceeds, however, the stress transfer length d gradually shortens since the stiffness of the composite increases. This indicates that strain values measured by FBGs depend on the sensor position along the optical fiber, meaning that the sensor tail length has a significant effect on the sensitivity of the FBG sensor.

In order to evaluate the shear-lag effect on the sensitivity of short-tailed FBG sensors, a preliminary test was conducted. Figure 6 shows the schematic of the specimen. Three FBG sensors (Fujikura Ltd., cladding diameter 125 μ m, polyimide-coating

Fig. 6 Schematic of specimen to evaluate effect of tail length on sensor sensitivity (with vacuum and no autoclave pressure).

diameter $150\mu\text{m}$, grating length 1mm) with different tail length of 2, 10, or 50 mm were embedded at the through-thickness center of unidirectional carbon/epoxy laminates (T700S/2592, Toray Industries, Inc., $[90_{50}]$, $100\text{mm}\times 100\text{mm}$, thickness 7mm). The specimen was cured without using an aluminum tool plate in an autoclave under ambient pressure in this test. Hence, vacuum bagging films covered both sides of the specimen surface, and vacuum was applied before heating the specimen. It

is important to note that the specimen edge was 50mm away from the sealant tape and constraint on the specimen is minimized. Only the fiber-direction was constrained by the sealant tape, which was necessary to reinforce and protect egress points of the sensors. Hence the composite specimen could freely deform in the through-thickness and in-plane transverse directions. The heating rate was set to $2^\circ\text{C}/\text{min}$ and the cure temperature was 90°C with 4.5h holding. After cure, the specimen was naturally cooled down. Preliminary tests using differential scanning calorimetry (DSC-60, Shimadzu Co.) yielded that the glass transition temperature of the carbon/epoxy reached 120°C after the cure cycle utilized, confirming that the specimen vitrified before cooling. The optical fibers were illuminated by an amplified spontaneous emission (ASE) light source (AQ2141, Ando Electric Co., Ltd.) through an optical channel selector (AQ3540, Ando Electric Co., Ltd.), and the reflection spectra from the FBGs and their center wavelength values were measured by an optical spectrum analyzer (AQ6317, Ando Electric Co., Ltd.) with sampling interval of 15sec. Embedded K-type thermocouples measured the temperature change in synchronization with the optical equipments, and the obtained value was utilized to compensate the temperature contribution to the FBG sensor response and to calculate the axial strain ϵ from Eq. (3).

Figure 7 shows the temperature and strain change

Fig. 7 Change in temperature, strain, and degree of cure.

measured. Also plotted are the degree of cure (DOC) and the cure shrinkage strain determined by standard techniques (i.e., DSC and TMA) under the same temperature profile. The DOC was determined by DSC-60 (Shimadzu Co., sample weight 4.7mg) and the cure shrinkage was evaluated by TMA-60 (Shimadzu Co., sample size 6mm×6mm, sample thickness 2.6mm, applied force 0.1N). The temperature curve in Fig. 7 showed slight overshoot due to the exothermal cure reaction. Before gelation, the FBG sensors measured strain change probably due to specimen thermal deformation and resin flow, which may give new physical insight into prepreg compaction and its effect on the cure process. However, this study focuses on strain development after gelation, and thus the strain at the gel point was set to be zero to facilitate the comparison between the three sensors. When the DOC reached 0.6, the FBG strains began to decrease (i.e., onset of gelation), successfully measuring cure shrinkage strain. The sensor with a 50mm tail measured almost the same strain as TMA. This result confirms that fiber-optic-based cure shrinkage characterization is valid and reliable. Hereafter, 50mm-tail sensors will be utilized as reference sensors giving true values of cure shrinkage strain. However, the magnitude of strain change decreased with decrease in the sensor tail length due to the aforementioned shear-lag effect. Finally, the short-tailed sensor (2mm-tail) measured only about half the strain of the long-tailed sensor (50mm-tail). Nevertheless, the result obtained confirmed that short-tailed sensors can sensitively capture cure shrinkage, and that one can obtain a true value of cure shrinkage strain by performing an appropriate correction. The simplest approach may be doubling the strain measured by a 2mm-tail sensor, and this rough approach is utilized hereafter. In the next section, short-tail FBG sensors are utilized to characterize cure shrinkage in unidirectional composites under an industrial condition.

3 Characterizing Direction-Dependent Cure Shrinkage In UD Composites

3.1 Materials and methods

Figure 8 depicts the schematic of specimens utilized. In addition to the test under the industrial condition with a tool, vacuum bagging, and autoclave pressure

of 0.4MPa (Fig. 8 (b)), a test without a tool was also conducted (Fig. 8 (a)), which is similar to the test in the previous section. The same carbon/epoxy (T700S/2592 Toray Industries, Inc.) was used, and the tool material was aluminum. Three FBG sensors (Fujikura Ltd., cladding diameter 125 μ m, polyimide-coating diameter 150 μ m, grating length 1mm) were embedded in each specimen; one short-tailed FBG sensor with a 2mm-tail in the through-thickness direction, one short-tailed FBG sensor with a 2mm-tail in the in-plane direction, and one long-tailed FBG sensor with a 50mm-tail in the in-plane direction. The position of the FBG sensor in the through-thickness direction was precisely controlled, as illustrated in Figure 8 (a). Both specimens were heated at a rate of 2°C/min, and were then cured at 90°C for 4h. After the temperature dwell in the test under the industrial condition, the autoclave pressure and vacuum were relieved to demold the specimen and to fully release so-called “tool-part interaction”, which is the frictional constraint on the specimen from the tool [1-3]. Effects of tool-part interaction on cure shrinkage were evaluated by comparing these two tests.

3.2 Results and discussion

Figure 9 shows the temperature and strain histories obtained. As in the test above, even though the strain changed by applying cure pressure and by heating, the strain at the gel point was set to be zero to facilitate the comparison between the sensors. In the test without a tool (Fig. 9 (a)), both of the short-tailed FBG sensors embedded in the through-thickness and in-plane directions measured almost the same strain of 1300 μ ϵ , indicating that “ideal” transversely isotropic cure shrinkage occurred (Fig. 10 (a)). The long-tailed FBG sensor measured double the strain of the short-tailed FBG, reproducing the result in the previous section (Fig. 7). In contrast, the specimen with a tool showed a totally different behavior (Fig. 9 (b)), indicating that transversely anisotropic cure shrinkage occurred (Fig. 10 (b)). The in-plane strain change was almost zero, as in the other researches. This is because the in-plane deformation of the curing specimen was constrained by the tool/part interaction through the interfacial shear stress (Fig. 10 (b)). Furthermore,

Fig. 8 Schematic of specimens. (a) Reference specimen without tool (with vacuum, and no autoclave pressure). (b) “Industrial-condition” specimen with tool, vacuum, and autoclave pressure of 0.4MPa.

Fig. 9 Temperature and strain change. (a) Reference specimen without tool. (b) Specimen with tool.

Fig. 10 Schematic of cure shrinkage under different conditions. (a) Transversely isotropic cure under no-tool condition. (b) Transversely anisotropic cure under industrial condition with tool.

after demolding and thus after releasing the tool/part interaction, the strain values did not change significantly. This behavior is attributed to viscoelastic nature of the curing composite and the transition from the rubbery state to the glassy state [21, 22]. During curing, stress induced by the constraint from the tool immediately relaxed due to the short relaxation time of the curing resin in the rubbery state, resulting in low residual stress. And the constrained deformation (i.e., zero in-plane shrinkage) was frozen into the specimen through the rubber-glass transition since the relaxation time dramatically increased during the vitrification. In contrast, the through-thickness value of $2900\mu\epsilon$ was almost double the one in the test without a tool. The rough correction estimates the through-thickness cure shrinkage strain to be $5800\mu\epsilon$. It can be understood that, since the in-plane deformation was constrained during cure, the volumetric contraction by chemical cure of the relatively incompressible rubbery resin took the form of the larger shrinkage in the out-of-plane direction (i.e., Poisson effect). In general laminates like quasi-isotropic ones, in-plane transverse deformation of each constituting unidirectional layer is constrained by the neighboring layers. The above result implies that cure shrinkage of each layer is transversely anisotropic, as indicated in Ref [23] using cross-ply laminates with TMA-based measurement.

4 Conclusions

This study developed a fiber-optic-based technique for in-situ characterization of direction-dependent cure shrinkage in thermoset fiber-reinforced composites. A procedure to embed fiber Bragg grating (FBG) sensors in composite out-of-plane directions was first established, and short-tailed FBG sensors embedded in through-thickness and in-plane directions clarified direction-dependent cure shrinkage in autoclaved unidirectional carbon/epoxy. The developed technique will be a powerful tool to evaluate cure shrinkage in complex-shaped parts and to validate process simulation tools.

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